

REDEFINING MECHATRONICS TO FIT MODERN SYSTEMS AND TRENDS

Thesis

The traditional way of defining mechatronics does not quite give a true picture of what mechatronics is today. This is largely due to the technological advancements and scientific discoveries that have reshaped how we practice mechatronics today.

Background

Engineering can be compared to an archipelago, consisting of isolated islands that often hinder productivity in different fields. In order for modern manufacturing systems, planes, cars, and computers to function effectively, there needs to be a harmonious integration of various technologies. Recognising this crucial need, Japan's engineers, have been designing electromechanical product subsystems for optimal performance for over 20 years. Among these Japanese engineers, one notable figure is KO Kikuchi, who is credited with coining the term Mechatronics. (Comerford, 1994)

Mechatronics is an interdisciplinary field of engineering that combines the traditional understanding of computer science, electronics, optics, hydraulics, pneumatics, and mechanical engineering in a way that works well together. (Pannaga, Ganesh, & Gupta, 2013)

The ability to operate across all the fields of technology needs to be emphasised more in Mechatronics. However, this is not to suggest that a Mechatronics professional should lack a depth of knowledge in specific discipline; instead, it may be suggested that this depth is modified by an awareness and comprehension of all the fields that make up Mechatronics. (Bradley, 2015)

Method

Several schools and companies specialising in the field of mechatronics in both South Africa and Germany were visited. A review of the South Africa and German Mechatronics curriculums was conducted. Conversation interviews with subject matter experts were held, working in education and factory sectors. Visited and participated in the Mechatronics competitions to systematically analyse how mechatronics is being conducted. A search was conducted on several academic sources using keyword “Mechatronics” articles and books published between 1970 and 2024 were included in the review.

Findings

Mechatronics in education is being treated as a combination of different fields, which are being taught in isolation to each other. Usually with practical projects of integration only taking place towards the end the term/ year.

There is lack of balance between the mechatronic disciplines, in particular IT: Software development, networking, microcontrollers, and robotics are neglected.

It is often a case that the facilitator at the school is a specialist in a Mechanical or electrical subject.

Conclusion

The integration of mechanical systems with electronic control has increased since the invention of programmable controllers. Modern automated systems, such as coffee machines, lifts, robotics, Aircrafts, and autonomous cars, require technology from all branches of mechatronics to function.

A mechatronic specialist's genius lies in their ability to analyse, design, assemble, wire, program, and commission automated systems. These systems include distributing, filling, packaging, sorting, robotics and more. They use logical, efficient, cost-effective, primitive, and sustainable approach. Additionally, Mechatronic specialist is able to design, and produce parts that are needed to retrofit and integrate different systems.

Works Cited

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